

Analysis of land use in the municipality of Gandu, Southern Bahia Lowlands: Interaction of cocoa crop with the Atlantic Forest biome

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ABSTRACT

The present research aims to analyze the land use in the municipality of Gandu, in the Southern Bahian Lowlands, and the interaction of the cocoa crop with the Atlantic Forest biome. As a methodology, theoretical and empirical surveys were carried out on phytophysiognomic diversity, land use and some species of the Atlantic Forest biome, as well as their agroecological relationship with cocoa crop. Interviews were made and questionnaires were applied on the relationship between cocoa production and the forest, field visits to cocoa farms, photographs of the forest (camera), cocoa cultivation in the municipality and also the identification of species with greater incidence in the landscape, use of the GIS (Geographic Information System) system as a geographic database for the analysis of geospatial data and generation of a map of location and land use. The results obtained reveal that most of the interviewees say that there has been degradation in the vegetation cover of the biome in recent decades, the vast majority say that the preservation of the forest is associated with the cultivation of cocoa, and that without it, the devastation of the forest was greater for the implementation of other crops such as cattle raising, bananas and subsistence crops at the time of the witches' broom. The fieldwork, together with the satellite images, shows that the forest is quite altered and this is associated with the use of the land: called capoeirinha, capoeira and capoeirão and more or less preserved fragments of the native ombrophilous forest in mountainous areas. It is concluded that the crop relationship is the most recurrent and oldest land use practice in the municipality of Gandu-Ba and that even with the changes in the dense ombrophilous forest, the cocoa crop contributes to the conservation of the Atlantic Forest biome through its Agroforestry System (AFS) that conserves part of the forest for exotic shading.

Keywords: Land use, Cocoa, Agroforestry, Atlantic Forest, Bahia.

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INTRODUCTION

The municipality of Gandu is in the Mesoregion of Southern Bahia, at latitude $-39^{\circ}.47'W$ of longitude (Figure 01). Its historicity is directly linked to the agricultural development and diffusion of cocoa culture, mainly due to the geographical and phytogeographic attributes of the region in which it is located, with emphasis on the humid tropical climate (rainfall regime without dry season) and Dense Ombrophilous Forest of Atlantic Forest.

By observing the reality of the municipality in question, especially in what says that the development of the first villages and urban areas had as their main pillar the production of cocoa that altered the Atlantic Forest biome in fragments of forest, pastures and cities, roads and other works of man. From this perspective, this research aims to analyze the land use and the interaction of cocoa crop: the consequences of such agricultural intervention in the biome in question in the present municipality.

The immersion of this research comprises the investigation of elements and relationships that permeate land use in the micro-region of the Southern Bahian Lowlands, specifically, in the municipality of Gandu, among these are: characteristics of the local phytophysiology and its connection with the cocoa monoculture system in deforestation and preservation of forest biodiversity, in addition to the historical process of cocoa cultivation, the colonization of the region and the exploitation of the Atlantic Forest for economic purposes with impacts on the biome. A general case study of the local phytophysiological attributes in different areas of the municipality was also carried out, in order to reveal the situation of degraded environments and the landscape potential of some areas within the municipal perimeter.

In this line, PEREIRA (2017) highlights environmental degradation as the loss of the environmental potential of a given area, a geographical unit or biome, thus, the environmental impact caused by man interferes with the resilience of environmental systems, the capacity and time for natural recovery.

In terms of environmental degradation, deforestation is the main problem that occurs in a region, although other correlated impacts can also be identified, such as the loss of quality and quantity of surface waters; indiscriminate use of pesticides that can contaminate water sources; silting of rivers; decrease in the availability of water in aquifers.

From the perspective of environmental degradation, according to SOS MATA ATLÂNTICA (2022), the Atlantic Forest is one of the most degraded biomes in Brazil, with large rates of landscape alteration and loss of biodiversity. According to INPE (2019), in 2019, the Atlantic Forest biome covered only 12.4% of native forests in their original extension, the result of a succession of environmental impacts, which occurred over time, in the process of occupation and use of the land.

For Vilas Boas and Nóbrega (2021), the environmental profile of the current scenario in which the Forest biome is located, constitutes a junction of fragmented areas, where in some places, ecological corridors form, which reinforces the need to preserve these environments, especially the forest fragments that are still preserved and that have not suffered or are found with insignificant anthropic actions.

The forest fragments found in the Atlantic Forest biome can be characterized as hotspots that have high rates of biodiversity and endemism, conserving the genetic bank of the species, subspecies and varieties found (fauna and flora) and the habitat.

In Law 11.428, which defines the conservation, protection, regeneration, and use of the Atlantic Forest biome, all forest remnants falling into the category of primary and secondary initial, medium and advanced regeneration forest, contributes to the creation of U.C. Conservation Units, as they play a fundamental role in the conservation of ecosystems.

Regarding the use and occupation of land in the Atlantic Forest biome, in the low-south of Bahia, there was a great process of environmental degradation, especially the dense ombrophilous forest, caused by the anthropic actions initiated by the colonizers until the present day, with deforestation as the main environmental problem that occurred in the region, although other correlated impacts can also be identified.

Understanding the current situation of the Atlantic Forest biome in a given region is essential for the planning and management of a watershed. In this sense, this research aims to analyze land use in the municipality of Gandu-Ba and the interaction of cocoa culture with the Atlantic Forest biome.

Figure 01 – Location of the research area, Gandu, Bahia.
Gandu - BA: Mapa de Localização (2023)

METHODS

Gandu is in a tropical zone. As a result, the climate is strong megathermal, according to Thornthwaite. The air masses that act in the area are the Atlantic Tropical and the east and southeast trade winds. Sporadically, trough low pressure centers form tropical instability lines, generating heavy rainfall, mainly in spring and summer with an annual average between 1700 and 1800mm. The trade winds usually cause stable weather, but when associated with the great humidity in the ocean, brought by the Atlantic Polar Mass, they cause a large amount of rainfall.

At the beginning of the colonization of this region, incursions were carried out in order to analyze the soil and the landscape potential for the implementation of the cocoa culture. By finding an extensive area of humid tropical forest, the environmental standards required for cocoa production (high rainfall, shade of native trees, organic layer on the soils, ecosystem diversity) were met.

To investigate this agroecological interaction, the following methodological procedures were adopted: studies and theoretical surveys on phytophysiological diversity, land use and some species of the Atlantic Forest biome, in addition to cocoa cultivation. According to the conceptions of several authors of physical geography (appropriating the geographical category of landscape), as well as research on cocoa production and its relationship with the biome.

After these observations, a face-to-face monitoring of cocoa farms in the municipality of Gandu – Ba was carried out, in addition to the characterization research of species with the highest

incidence in the landscape through the Planet application. This is based on a worldwide catalog of species identified in the field by a wide range of botanical researchers and other scholars in the field. The images of plants for identification are leaves, fruits and flowers. The app immediately presents the most likely species, but it is necessary to have prior knowledge of taxonomy, ecology and biogeography of the species you want to identify. In this stage, land use areas were selected, such as: pasture, cocoa crops, cocoa crops (cocoa-cabruca), and also with other crops, primary and secondary forests. (Nóbrega & Boas, 2020).

A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed in the adjacent areas of the municipality. The guiding axes for the distribution of the questionnaires were the profiles: rural workers, old residents of the municipality, city hall employees, members of the rural union, younger residents of the municipality who had some contact with the cocoa-cabruca agroforestry system, as well as questions for the characterization of the degraded biome and residents' impressions about transformations in the fauna/flora landscapes. A case study was carried out on the relationship between cocoa production and the implementation of cocoa-cabruca systems and total felling system, introduced by the Executive Committee of the Cocoa Farming Plan (CEPLAC), and economic practice of cocoa culture.

As a GIS (Geographic Information System) tool, SigBahia was used as a base. First, the municipalities shape was used to cut out the municipality of Gandu (which was selected and exported). The vegetation map of the same cartographic base that has the land use classes made by the water resources department when it created SigBahia was used. Then, the base/vegetation/use classes were cut using the municipality of Gandu as a reference. This data was taken to the GIS application, Qgis, where the base of use classes was loaded and the classification tool was used in the "style" tab. In addition, the IBGE-IBGE contornos –IBGE municipalities database was used to generate the location map of the municipality of Gandu.

Parallel to geoprocessing, another methodology to be used will be photography and its respective analyses. This study will contribute to the investigation on land use in the municipality with regard to cocoa crops, pastures and areas in recovery, but also the different stages of dense ombrophilous forest (herbaceous stratum, shrub stratum, lower herbaceous stratum or understory, middle tree stratum, roof or canopy, upper tree stratum: emergent trees) in adjacent areas.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Relationship between cocoa plantations and Dense Ombrophilous Forests is more than an agricultural practice; It is an agroforestry crop or system. The first system implemented was the cocoa-cabruca or exotic shading, contributing to the better evolution of cocoa trees, soil conservation

in addition to the meso and microscale climatic elements, favoring greater humidity in the region due to the great evapotranspiration that occurred in dense ombrophilous forests.

Although the cocoa-cabruca system is a less aggressive practice to the aforementioned biome, the issue of environmental preservation in the region is little addressed. This presents a problem in the short and long term. Many producers, despite using the shade of native trees, fight the ecological competition of flora with the cutting of trees. In addition, we must take into account the fires for the creation of pastures. The situation was intensified with the spread of the witches' broom plague from 1989 onwards, causing not only an economic crisis, but also an environmental one, since it was necessary to resort to other sources of income, such as livestock.

The map in figure 2 represents the form of land use in the referred municipality, showing the scope and distribution of the cocoa-cabruca system, the areas of forest in recovery (secondary forest) and, to a lesser extent, the urban area in the municipality of Gandu.

Figure 2 – Land use map of the municipality of Gandu.

Agroforestry systems such as cocoa-cabruca are less aggressive to the biome. The occurrence of crop devastation due to the witches' broom fungus contributes to the deforestation of native areas. In this scenario, the localities affected by this pest are used for pasture, the implantation of other crops that do not necessarily need shading, such as bananas and cassava, and for the use of wood for locksmiths or as firewood. The preservation of already fragmented areas of the Atlantic Forest biome is of paramount importance for its permanence, in addition to the conservation of biodiversity and habitats for endemic species of fauna and flora (Table 1).

Table 1 – Some tree species of the Atlantic Forest found in Gandu and land use.

FAMILY	SPECIES	COMMON NAME	LIFESTYLE	Land use
<i>Lecythidaceae</i>	<i>Cariniana legalis</i> (Mart.) Kuntze	Jequitibá	Macrofaneróa	Cocoa plantation
<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Ficus Insipada</i> (Willd)	Gameleira	Mesmerizing	Cocoa plantation
<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Erytrina verna</i> (Vell)	Aletrine	Mesmerizing	
<i>Bignonecea</i>	<i>Tabebuia chrysotricha</i> (Mart. Ex A.DC.)	Ypê	Mesmerizing	Cocoa plantation
<i>Rutaceae</i>	<i>Balfourodendron riedelianum</i>	Guatambú	Macrofaneróa	Pasture
<i>Anacardiaceae</i>	<i>Myracrodruo Urundeuva</i>	Black Aroeira	Mesmerizing	Pasture
<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Bauhinia forficata</i> Link	Cow's Foot	Microfanerófit	Cocoa/banana cultivation
<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Caesalpinia echinata</i> Lam.	Brazilwood	Mesmerizing	Cocoa plantation
<i>Meliaceae</i>	<i>Cedrela fissilis</i> Vell	Cedar-rose	Macrofaneróa	Cocoa plantation
<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Caesalpinia férrea</i> C. Mart	Ironwood	Mesmerizing	Pasture
<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Peltophorum dubium</i>	Canafistula	Microfanerófit	Pasture
<i>Bignoniaceae</i>	<i>Jakaranda Mikranta</i> Cham.	Cabobão	Microfanerófit	Cocoa plantation
<i>Malvaceae</i>	<i>Luehea divaricata</i> Mart.	Horsewhip- Kid	Mesmerizing	Cocoa plantation

Source: Boas, Nóbrega & Santos (2021) and The World Flora online, 2024.

The relationships between the agroforestry systems used in the municipality play an important role in the partial conservation of the biome, as they use the landscape potential of the present biome for the implementation of the cocoa crop understory. In the present survey, it was reported that 75% of the interviewees recognize preservation or practice that is not very intensive to the biome, while 25% do not understand such a relationship. (Figure 03)

Figure 03 – Interview with residents about the relationship between the preservation of the Atlantic Forest and cocoa culture.

Do you believe that cocoa production can help preserve the Atlantic Forest? 28 answers

Source: Boas, Nóbrega & Santos (2021).

Regarding the relationship between phytophysiognomy and land use, it was evidenced that a very common type of land use in the area is pasture for cattle raising, whose relief is predominantly flat and gently undulating with approximately 90 meters of altitude (Figure 04). In the vicinity passes

the Gandu River (perennial river), which influences the formation of small swamps/floodplains. The species with the highest incidence in the herbaceous mat were collected for a characterization of the flora. Therefore, the following were found in this environment: *Sphagneticola trilobata* (L.) Asteraceae, herbaceous; *Piper hispidum* (S.W) Piperaceae, vine; *Thunbergia alata* (Boje rex Sims) Acanthaceae, bindweed; *Alternanthera philoxeroides* (Mart) Amaranthaceae herbaceae; *Epidendrum ibaguense* (Kunth) Orchidacea (epiphyte).

Figure 04 – Typical landscape of land use in the municipality of Gandu

Source: Boas, Nóbrega & Santos (2021).

In one of the delimited areas of the municipality of Gandu, a visit was made to a cocoa plantation in the southern part of the municipality of Gandu, near the edge of the forest, in a place with dissected topography at an altitude of around 174 meters. It is a tropical rainforest whose coordinates are 13° 76' S, 39° 49' W. During the characterization of the flora, different species of both herbaceous carpet and epiphytes were collected, among them; *Nidularium billbergiodes* (Shult and Shult.F, Bromeliaceae epiphyte), *Lantana triphobia* (L, Verbenaceae herbaceous), *Bothriochloa ischaemum* (L. Keng, Poaceae - herbaceous), *Cyperus esculentis* (L. Cyperaceae - herbaceous), *Viola odorata* (L., Violaceae - herbaceous), *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) - herbaceous), *Dorycnium pentaphyllum* (Scop), Legumiseae - herbaceous, *Mimosa pudica* (L.), Leguminoseae - herbaceous, *Heracleum sphondylium* (L.) Apeaceae - herbaceous. (Figure 05).

Figure 05 – Landscape with cocoa and native species of the Atlantic Forest.

Source – Boas, Nóbrega & Santos (2021).

The visit was made to a cocoa plantation in the cultivation of bananas, cassava and oranges in the southwest of the municipality, whose coordinates are: Latitude 13° 81´ South and Longitude of 39° and 63´ West, with V-shaped valley topography in an area of forest edge with an approximate altitude of 335 meters. The location of this property in a place with a higher density of dense ombrophilous forest and also the relief contribute to the strong presence of shading. In this sense, a research was carried out to identify species of both forest canopy, emergent, herbacies and epiphytic life forms, including cocoa. List of species found in these areas: *Momordica charantia* (L.) Cucurbitaceae, herbaceous carpet of capoeira with emerging trees and cocoa, *Dactylis glamerata* (L.) Herbaceae present in capoeira, *Tradescantia zebrina* (Bosse), Commeliaceae, *Xanthosoma taiba* (E. G) Araceae, *Osmunda claytonia* (L.) Osmundaceae of the pteridophyte group, *Rubus phoenicolasius* (Maxim) Rosaceae, *Pragmites australis* (Cav. Trin ex Steud), Poaceae. The forest is quite degraded in several parts of the municipality with a physiognomy similar to that of figure 6, where the tallest trees reach 20m in height.

Source: Nóbrega & Meguro (2003).

CONCLUSION

The interface of cocoa farming with the Atlantic Forest biome and the practice of production under exotic shade say a lot about the conservation of the dense ombrophilous forest that dominates the region. In this scenario, this research seeks a balance between production and conservation, which can be achieved through the implementation of agroforestry systems, which act towards the valorization and regional economic diversification, as well as the preservation of already degraded areas with a high rate of biodiversity found in the municipality of Gandu.

Agroforestry systems provide soil recovery for agricultural and livestock development, socioeconomic and sociocultural production, and environmental preservation. In this way, the management of agroforestry should also trigger the economic strengthening of local/regional farmers, as well as the expansion of production and diversification of agricultural products, in association with the preservation of the biodiversity of the native biome domain, promoting sustainability. This production system can contribute positively to the revitalization of crops and preservation of the genetic bank that is threatened, making it as similar as possible to the local ecosystem in structure, composition and functionality.

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